

AGREEMENTS APPLICABLE TO THE TRANSFER OF INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY OBJECTS TO THE THIRD PARTIES

Egamova Dilrabo Tolibovna

Doctoral student of Tashkent State University of Law

e-mail: dilya.tolibovna@gmail.com

Phone: +998 88 828 9272

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Annotation.

In this article, concepts and information about the ways in which intellectual property objects are commercialized are regulated by contracts, and the main concepts and information are explained on the basis of our national legislation. In addition, it has been shown that various ways can be used for the further development of this field in our country, and the fact that the laws and regulations stipulated in contracts are important in preventing problems arising in this field. cited.

Key words: author, contract, contract types, trademark, license, license agreements, mandatory license.

Under the agreement on the creation and use of the results of intellectual activity, the author undertakes to create a work, invention or other result of intellectual activity in the future and to grant exclusive rights to use this result to a customer who is not his employer. Every creative person can organize his intellectual activity at his own will, on his own initiative, on the basis of his own funds, or on the basis of a contract based on the order of another non-employer. Personal non-property and absolute rights to the result of creative activity created on the basis of the author's own initiative and funds belong only to him. He freely appropriates the absolute rights to the object, which is the product of creative activity.¹

Therefore, copyright is a personal non-property right and belongs only to the person who created the result of intellectual activity with his creative work. The copyright cannot be transferred or given to another person. The author's right to the result of creative activity belongs only to the creator, it cannot be alienated from him in any way, on any basis, and cannot be transferred to someone else. For this reason, the transfer of copyright to another person based on an agreement or contract: sale, gift or relinquishment in favor of other persons is not considered valid, even if it is done by the author's free will,

¹ Okyulov O., Rakhmonkulov H. Intellectual property: general rules and special objects. – T. :TDYI publishing house 2004y 38-p.

discretion and desire². We are sure that personal property rights cannot be transferred from this information to other persons.

Thus, we can see that the conditions of legal formalization of full or partial transfer of absolute rights to other people are clearly defined in the legislation. For example, in Article 1035 of the FC of the Republic of Uzbekistan - property rights belonging to the owner of exclusive rights to an object of intellectual property can be fully or partially transferred by the owner of the right to another person under the contract, unless otherwise provided by law, as well as these absolute rights are inherited and transferred in the order of legal succession when the legal entity - the owner of the right is reorganized. The transfer of property rights under the contract or their transfer in the order of universal legal succession does not cause the transfer or limitation of the non-alienable and non-transferable absolute rights of copyright. This article states that the terms of the agreement on the transfer or limitation of such rights are invalid by themselves.

A license agreement is an important civil legal instrument that allows third parties to use intellectual property objects, and this agreement is an agreement to allow the use of intellectual property objects³. The license agreement is an important civil legal instrument that allows third parties to use intellectual property objects. A license agreement is an agreement allowing the use of an intellectual property object. The owner of exclusive rights, that is, the owner of a patent, the owner of a trademark, the owner of an object of copyright, the owner of undisclosed information, a license to grant to third parties his rights to use the object under legal protection in the prescribed manner and on the basis of certain conditions (permit) is called.

According to the established rules, the property rights belonging to the owner of exclusive rights to an object of intellectual property can be fully or partially transferred by the owner of the right to another person under the contract. Also, the rights provided for in this shall have only a property character, with the exception of personal rights. Transferred property rights are derived from absolute rights and must belong only to the right holder. Property rights mean the rights of the right holder to use the object of intellectual property for personal use or to make it available for a fee. When the property right is fully transferred, the owner of the right loses these rights and these

² Okyulov O., Rakhmonkulov H. Theoretical and practical problems of the legal status of intellectual property. – T. :TDYI publishing house 2004y 78-p.

³ Okyulov O., Rakhmonkulov H. Theoretical and practical problems of the legal status of intellectual property. – T. :TDYI publishing house 2004y 78-p.

rights arise in third persons. When the property right is partially transferred, the owner of the right retains a certain part of it and transfers the remaining part. Thus, in such a situation, a contract is concluded between the owner of the property right and the person to whom this right is fully or partially transferred. When concluding such contracts, unless otherwise provided for, Chapter 26 of the FC of the Republic of Uzbekistan - the concept and terms of the contract, Chapter 27 - the rules for changing the terms of the contract and canceling the contract shall be applied⁴.

In the contract, the names of the contracting parties - the owner of the exclusive right to the object of intellectual property and the person to whom the property rights arising from the exclusive right are transferred, if the exclusive right is based on the legal protection label issued by the state body authorized to the object of intellectual property if it has been created, the name and registration number of this label, its validity period, the content and volume of the transferred property right, the conditions of its use, the term if the contract is concluded on a fee basis, the amount of the fee to be paid and the order of payment, rights of the right holder to control its use when the property right is partially transferred, other rights and obligations of the parties, liability of the parties for breaching the terms of the contract, etc. should be specified. The contract must be signed by the parties and formalized in the appropriate form. The law stipulates that the form of the contract should be different for different objects of intellectual property rights. When transferring property rights to copyright objects, the contract must be drawn up in writing and notarized. If the authority of absolute right is created on the basis of the legal protection label - patent, certificate issued by the state body in relation to the object of intellectual property right, then the contract on the transfer of the property right is drawn up in writing, notarized and submitted to the competent state office. must be registered. This rule also applies to know-how. Otherwise, the contract is not valid.

In our current legislation, we can see that there are exceptions to the above-mentioned rules regarding the transfer of property rights arising from exclusive rights to certain intellectual property objects by the right holder. For example, according to Part 3 of Article 1109 of the CC of the Republic of Uzbekistan, it is not allowed to transfer the right to use the name of the place where the goods were issued to other persons by the right holder, and if such an agreement is concluded, it is considered invalid.

⁴ Okyulov O., Rakhmonkulov H. Theoretical and practical problems of the legal status of intellectual property. – T. :TDYI publishing house 2004y, 86-p.

In the case of the transfer of absolute rights in the order of inheritance and in the order of legal succession, if there is a certificate of inheritance issued by a notary, a label of legal protection, the relevant document of the competent state office on the registration of this label in the name of the new owner of the absolute right is obtained and it is registered with the state. must be carried out. The transfer of property rights under the contract or their transfer in the order of universal legal succession does not cause the transfer or limitation of copyright and other non-alienable and non-transferable absolute rights. Such contracts are considered invalid⁵.

Also, based on the FC of the Republic of Uzbekistan, this code states that the provisions of the license agreement are applied to the contract that provides for the transfer of the exclusive right to another person during its validity period. According to it, the party (licensor) who has the exclusive right to the means reflecting the result of intellectual activity or private signs under the license agreement allows the other party (licensee) to use the object of intellectual property.

Although the license agreement is similar to the traditional sale and lease agreements according to its legal nature, it differs from these agreements in its own aspects. These are: first, sales and lease agreements are based on the seller's or lessor's property right or right in rem. The license agreement is based on the licensor's exclusive right to the object of intellectual property. Secondly, the property is transferred to the buyer or lessee on the basis of sale or property lease, and the property can be owned by both parties at the same time. In most cases, there is no need to hand over the object of absolute right: the content of the invention, industrial design, or the effect of the trademark has been announced and everyone has the opportunity to get acquainted with it. This object can be used simultaneously by the licensor and by third parties of an indefinite scope.

A license agreement is a fee agreement. Generally, two types of payment forms are widely used in the payment of fees under the license agreement. These are payment of all fees at once (lump sum payment) and allocation of income from products produced or sold under license (royalty) ⁶. Sometimes these two forms can be used together. In this case, it is possible to pay a guaranteed fixed amount of fee at first, and then allocate a share of the profit in each specified

⁵ Okyulov O., Rakhmonkulov H. Theoretical and practical problems of the legal status of intellectual property. - T.: TDYI publishing house, 2004, p. 87

⁶ Okyulov O., Rakhmonkulov H. Theoretical and practical problems of the legal status of intellectual property. - T.: TDYI publishing house, 2004, p 92.

period. In some cases, the fee may be received in kind. Also, the payment method is determined based on the agreement of the parties.

The agreement on the transfer of the right to use the object of intellectual property by the licensee to another person is a sublicense (secondary or derivative license) agreement. The licensee has the right to conclude a sublicense agreement only in the cases stipulated in the license agreement. The licensee shall be liable to the licensor for the actions of the additional licensee, unless otherwise stipulated in the license agreement⁷.

Laws also include types of mandatory license, open license, and compulsory license⁸

Compulsory license - Article 40 of the Law on Selection Achievements basically stipulates that the owner of the patent does not use the selection achievement in the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan for three years from the date of the patent and refuses to conclude a license agreement, and if not using this selection achievement is in the interests of society. It is stated in this law that the person who wants to use this selection achievement can apply to the court with a request to be granted an absolute compulsory license if it causes damage. Also, a compulsory license is not issued to any person, but only to a person who can ensure the use of other selection achievements in a manner that is permissible and in accordance with the license. A compulsory license does not prevent the owner of the patent from using the protected breeding achievement himself or from granting a license to use it to other persons. The Patent Office publishes information on the issuance of compulsory licenses.

Another type of compulsory license is a compulsory license. Pursuant to Article 32 of the Law on Inventions, Utility Models and Industrial Designs, an industry may use an object of industrial property based on the fact that the owner of the exclusive right has used another protected object and the right to it belongs to another natural or legal entity. If not received, he has the right to demand from the person who owns the right to grant a license to use the facility based on the conditions specified in the contract.

Open license terms apply to some objects of intellectual property rights. In accordance with Article 32 of the Law on Inventions, Utility Models and Industrial Designs, the patent owner may apply to the Patent Office to grant the right to use the industrial property object to any person. A license obtained in this manner is called an open license. A person seeking an open license must

⁷ Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Tashkent "Adolat" 2007, p 444 .

⁸ Okyulov O., Rakhmonkulov H. Theoretical and practical problems of the legal status of intellectual property. - T.: TDYI publishing house, 2004, p 93.

enter into a payment agreement or an exclusive license agreement with the patent owner. Disputes regarding the terms of the contract are heard in commercial courts. A patent owner's application for an open license cannot be withdrawn.

The use of exclusive rights in relation to intellectual property objects for commercial purposes, obligations and other civil-legal forms serves a worldwide turnover of one hundred billion dollars annually⁹ and the contract is an incomparable and universal legal tool in the regulation of social relations regarding the implementation of various business activities, the organization of production, the exchange of products between different forms of property and subjects,¹⁰ the contract occupies the main place in the legal means of using intellectual property objects in commercialization.

E.P. Gavrilov analyzes patent agreements and divides them into the following types: agreements on full or partial waiver of patent rights; patent rights co-ownership agreements, such as a general partnership agreement; founding agreements on the transfer of patent rights to the charter fund of full or limited partnerships, to the charter capital of limited liability or joint-stock companies, to production cooperatives as share contributions, to the property of a unitary enterprise, fund, institution; patent rights pledge agreement; sublicense notices¹¹

In conclusion, when intellectual property objects are transferred to third parties, mainly because the license agreement takes the leading place, let's clarify the effect of the license agreement, the validity of such agreements in other countries and the procedure for its application in our national legislation. we tried to. We think that the results of our research will help to improve this type of legislation in practice

In conclusion, it can be noted that concepts and information about how to regulate the commercialization of intellectual property objects using what kind of contracts have been given above. Also, we explained the main concepts and information based on our national legislation. Our main goal was to show that it is possible to use different ways to further develop this industry in our country. To date, further development of these types of commercialization in our country is one of the needs of today. Because the laws and regulations stipulated in

⁹ Gulyaev A.V. Means of individualization of legal entities, objects of civil rights // Current problems of private law regulation: Proceedings of the V international scientific conference of young scientists. Samara: Univer-group, 2005. P.439

¹⁰ Okyulov O., Rakhmonkulov H. Theoretical and practical problems of the legal status of intellectual property. - T.: TDYI publishing house 2004

¹¹ Гаврилов Э.П. патентные договоры: правовое регулирование//Патенты и лицензии. 2003. С 47-53.

contracts are important in preventing problems arising in this area, and their compliance with the law is gaining importance today.

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